

**COMPARATIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF MINIMALLY
INVASIVE SURGERY OF VASOMOTOR RHINITIS****Nurova Guzal Ubaydullaevna¹**<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2708-7874>,**Shodiyeva Maftuna Baqoevna²**¹⁻²Bukhara State Medical Institute named after Abu Ali Ibn Sino<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7223259>

One of the main and frequently occurring objective symptoms of chronic rhinitis is an increase in the volume of the lower nasal concha (NCR). To date, many technologies have been developed and used for the surgical treatment of a combined form of vasomotor and hypertrophic rhinitis.

Objective: To evaluate the effectiveness of radiowave surgery of vasomotor rhinitis.

Materials and methods of the study: The study was performed on 24 patients (15 women and 9 men) aged 21 to 52 years suffering from vasomotor rhinitis. The duration of the disease ranged from 2 to 8 years. Patients, depending on the type of surgery, are divided into two groups of 12 people. The patients underwent radio wave surgery of the lower nasal conchs under local anesthesia. The results were evaluated 2 weeks and 6 months after surgery based on the analysis of the patient's complaints before and after surgery, instrumental examination, endoscopy of the nasal cavity, examination of the main functions of the nose with the study of mucociliary transport and anterior active rhinomanometry.

Results: The analysis of the results of the study showed the disappearance of patient complaints, a noticeable decrease in the volume of NPR during objective examination, restoration of the mucous membrane, improvement of nasal breathing. This was confirmed by studying the indicators of the saccharin test, the total volume flow and the total resistance at a fixed pressure point of 150 Pa on the 14th day and 6 months after the operation.

Conclusions: Thus, radiowave surgery is an effective and less traumatic method for the treatment of vasomotor rhinitis, is simple and safe, therefore it can be successfully used in outpatient settings.